

TEACHING ECOLOGY TO STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION TO INSTILL ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY BEHAVIOUR

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Abstract. *In recent years, there has been a growing concern about the substantial decrease in opportunities for outdoor learning in schools and the limited knowledge students have of our common animals and plants in the nearest environment (e.g. Bebbington, 2005). It is also stressed that students should be taught about different ecosystems. However, in these curricula there are no explicit guidelines for how this instruction is supposed to be carried out and naturally there is a great variation in how teachers meet these demands. This article analyzes the results of a pedagogical and didactic experiment which was focused on the problem of teaching environmentally-friendly behaviors to university students. It is important to awaken students' curiosity and desire to know more about environmental issues in their regions so that students develop their own answers to problems. This research focus on understanding the potential of practical-experimental activities connected to ecology, in a relaxed and entertaining learning context, promotes the learning of environmentally-friendly behaviors. The analysis of the results obtained in the pedagogical and didactic experiment was based on the following categories: (a) teaching and learning methodology and teaching resources; (b) student perceptions. The findings revealed that the built teaching resources have enabled these student to understand the importance of having environmentally-friendly behaviors.*

Keywords: *Environmentally-friendly behaviors, Practical experimental activities, university children, Higher educator training*

We find that all curricular components should help to foster students' attitudes and values that enable them to become aware and be supportive citizens, empowering them to solve life's problems" (ME, 2009: 51). Preschool education is considered "the first stage of basic education in the education process throughout life, which complements the educational action of the family, with which it works in a close relationship, favoring the formation and the balanced development of the child with a view to her integration in society as an autonomous, free and solidary being" (ME, 2009: 15). In OCEPE, in the curricular area "Knowledge of the World" it is considered that the teaching and learning must be "rooted in the child's natural curiosity and desire to know and understand why. Curiosity is encouraged and extended in pre-school through opportunities to engage with new situations that are both opportunities for discovery and exploration of the world" (ME, 2009: 79). The various social, cultural and economic dynamics that the world faces today "require that education becomes a set of renewed missions, that only collective effort can face" (Carneiro, 1994 cited by Monteiro, 2009: 42). It is not enough to experience everyday contexts for the acquisition of scientific knowledge. According to Thiesen (2008: 8), "the more interdisciplinary the teaching, the higher the conceptual relations between different sciences, the more problematizing, stimulating, challenging and dialectic are teaching methods, the greater the possibility of understanding the subjects they learn". Activities developed in the kindergarten context should enable children to become autonomous and independent in relation to thought and the acquisition of know-how. The acquisition of know-how, necessary for their independence and

the need for greater autonomy, is an opportunity for choice and accountability" (ME, 2007: 53). Hence, after checking skills and difficulties, students should be prepared to experience those activities, in order to prepare them for positive interventions in their nearby surroundings.

FACTORS AFFECTING THE TEACHING OF ECOLOGY

Booth and Sinker (1979) identified the following issues as among those that contribute to preventing the effective teaching of ecology in schools:

- a) The nature of the subject.
- b) Difficulties and confusion about how to teach ecology.
- c) Examination syllabi and papers.
- d) Lack of confidence of teachers.
- e) Lack of facilities.

Vma (1988) found the following difficulties in teaching ecology as perceived by Nigerian teachers:

- a) Difficulties in the education system, such as lack of provision of appropriate teacher training.
- b) Syllabus difficulties, such as ecology not often being geared towards solving major biological problems.
- c) Problems of approach in ecology teaching which form the greater part of the perceived problems.

Vma (1988) also cited Moss and Theobald (1979) who found that the major difficulties in teaching ecology in Kenya were:

- a) The large amount of time required for teaching ecology is disproportionate in relation to other syllabus topics in four-year course leading to O-level.
- b) The weighting given to ecology in the syllabus is not reflected in the examination.
- c) Identification of local flora and fauna is often considered difficult.
- d) Finding a suitable habitat within the environs of a secondary school.
- e) The shortage of appropriate, inexpensive equipment.
- f) Lack of opportunities for making simple quantitative measurements and interpreting collected data.
- g) Insufficient teacher training, both pre-service and in-service, in the teaching of ecology.
- h) Maintenance of student interest during the study of ecology.

Although these findings were made about twenty years ago, they would seem to be valid even today, especially in South Africa. I will discuss the challenges confronting the teaching of ecology in Uzbekistan under two broad headings, namely; curriculum issues and the teacher factor. A survey undertaken in Uzbekistan showed that 'Nature Study', that forms a base for ecological learning, was hardly included in the curriculum of even the youngest classes. He further reported that ecology teaching at the secondary school level started in the third term of the final five-year course. Hale (1991) also reported that in England and Wales many universities have not gone beyond the nature table for their ecology. In South Africa, ecology is taught as late as grade 10. It may be argued, therefore, that the curriculum seeks to prepare students for examinations and does not emphasise the understanding of ecological concepts and sensitivity to their environments. The biology syllabus be designed in such a way as to teach aspects of ecology right from year one.

The cultural metabolism of most population does not follow the principles of

ecological sustainability. One hopes that science will solve environmental problems related to anthropocentric practices. However, nature needs a sustainable development which necessarily implies the adoption of environmentally-friendly behaviour. If, on the one hand, the relationship between economic development and environmental balance, which should underpin sustainable development, has been consensual between the political community and researchers in these areas, on the other hand the role of education is in most cases very different and controversial, having been the object of a wide range of analysis. Partaking in the ideals of those defending a critical awareness for this educational problem, education for sustainable development, in its multiple and renewed perplexities, is a truly challenging problem.

Conclusion. Result analysis for this pedagogical and didactic experiment highlighted the need for an assessment of the wider impact of the teaching and learning of ecology knowledge appropriation, designed in an interdisciplinary perspective (integrating mother tongue and art) and set in everyday situations to instill environmentally-friendly behaviour in the context of higher education. That is, it is necessary that other pedagogical and didactic resources of this type are designed, validated and implemented. This study is part of a wider research area, which aims to analyze methodologies of teaching and learning in science with students of universities. Higher education is a determining factor for learning and personal, educational and social inclusion, which should be the foundation for a responsible and active citizenship for all students. In this study it was concluded that the practical and experimental activities using an interdisciplinary perspective (integrating mother tongue and art) and a relaxed and entertaining learning context, constitute teaching and learning resources which foster learning of the environmentally-friendly behavior in students. Following a recreational and didactic orientation, activities should also encourage curiosity and develop reasoning.

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